

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Deliverables/Milestones

Document info

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0.1	Fotis Psomopoulos	2025/01/24	First draft
1.0.0	Fotis Psomopoulos,	2025/01/31	Final version
	Admin Check by Hub (CoS Portfolio Manager)		<i>(To revise section X)</i>
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Author List

Node	Institute	Name, surname	ORCID	Email
GR	CERTH	Fotis, Psomopoulos	0000-0002-0222-4273	fpsom@certh.gr
ES	BSC	Eva, Alloza	0000-0001-8385-9336	eva.alloza@bsc.es
SE	UU	Jessica, Lindvall	0000-0002-5042-8481	jessica.lindvall@scilifelab.se

Executive Summary

The deliverable consists of a comprehensive description of the key outcomes of the Training Platform during 2024 for inclusion in the ELIXIR Annual Report.

Deliverable

Authors/PREFERRED Contacts	Platform co-leads and Hub Platform Coordinators: Jessica Lindvall (SE) Fotis Psomopoulos (GR) Eva Alloza (ES) Katharina Heil (Hub) Mihail Anton (Hub)
Number of Services	Number of Platform services: 363
Content <500 words	<p>Aims/purpose of the Platform (once sentence):</p> <p>The main mission of the Training Platform (TrP) is to build and promote standards for training, and with this support and align to the training efforts and activities of the ELIXIR Nodes, establishing concrete synergies across the European and global training ecosystem.</p> <p>Any changes in co-leadership in 2024: None</p> <p><u>Scientific Programme 2024-28</u></p> <p>To ensure the continued cohesion and strategic alignment of the TrP community, we maintained the tradition of holding weekly Coordination calls (ExCo/Hub level) that are complemented with the monthly TrP calls. Additionally, to further facilitate and address any issues across work packages (WP), the new practice of the WP-Lead coordination calls was introduced. Overall, at the programme level, the Training Platform has progressed well, achieving all expected milestones and producing all the relevant deliverables.</p> <p>Some notable outputs of 2024 for the TrP include the updated Training Metrics Database, as well as the resource portal SPLASH describing the training lifecycle, both of which were an outcome of significant discussions within the TrP community over the year. Moreover, a first public version of the FAIR Training Handbook was released, demonstrating a significant contribution in the context of FAIR Training at a global level.</p>

Finally, TrP members were able to connect directly in the context of a number of events throughout the year, including the TrP F2F meeting (Prague, March 2024) and the All Hands Meeting (Uppsala, June 2024) where the TrP had a dedicated mini Symposium on the subject of *"Enriching synergies across the ELIXIR Training Platform and the Science Tier"*, complemented by two other workshops (*"A world-café approach to identify training-related needs across the ELIXIR ecosystem"* and *"Collaborative solutions for enhancing inclusiveness of training"*) and a new [updated poster](#).

Platform Services

In addition to the updated [Training Metrics Database](#) service, and the SPLASH website, significant effort was given within the TrP to ensure improved and aligned documentation of all Platform services, with the aim of dissemination and increasing uptake.

EU projects

The TrP was particularly active across a number of EU Projects, primarily in instances where multiple Nodes were involved. Of particular note are the following:

- EOSC4Cancer: members of the ELIXIR TrP actively contributed to a deliverable of the project around the design of Learning Paths ([EOSC4Cancer - Deliverable 5.1 - A guidance document for the EOSC4Cancer learning pathway](#))
- RITrainPlus: members of the TrP contributed to the design and delivery of a training course.
- [PHENET](#): members of the TrP contributed in training courses on the subject of Data management, as well as a coherent TtT activity.
- ELIXIR-STEERS: the ELITma modules were created and TtT courses were delivered

Collaborations within ELIXIR

The TrP is also actively engaging across a number of other ELIXIR Communities, Platforms and initiatives. Notably, at the Platform level, the TrP joined forces with the Data Platform towards defining a concrete process for reward and recognition across traditionally not recognized activities (such as training, curation, etc). Moreover, the activities of both the FAIR Training and the Learning Path Focus Groups are fully in alignment to the scope of the TrP objectives. Finally, and in the context of the new work programme, the two CoS ELITMa and Train-the-Trainer have been co-designed with TrP

members, with the goal of complementing and improving the already planned and ongoing activities.

Collaborations outside ELIXIR

A key activity of the TrP throughout 2024 was to ensure engagement and alignment with relevant efforts at the global level, building also on the strategic relationships established by ELIXIR. This activity encompasses all aspects of the TrP, from the delivery of training workshops (such as "[Introduction to ML](#)" for AU BioCommons), active participation to NIH coordination calls, as well as regularly scheduled alignment and cross-communication calls with the counterparts of the AU BioCommons Bioinformatics Training Cooperative. Participation in the [Global Bioinformatics Education Summit](#) leading the "Assessment of learning (short format training)" session.

Figure

Figure source:

 All Hands Training Platform Poster [2024] as published here <https://f1000research.com/posters/13-538>

Figure description: The ELIXIR Training SPLASH is a comprehensive user-centric platform built by the TrP members, consolidating resources through a consistent format to provide an accessible "one-stop-shop" for training activities across all phases of the training lifecycle.

Contact name and email address: Training Platform Coordination Team
training-exco@elixir-europe.org

Outcomes and Impacts of the deliverable

The deliverable comprehensively describes key outcomes of the Training Platform during 2024, as covered in the ELIXIR Annual Report.

Dissemination Plans

The ELIXIR Annual Report is a key document of the ELIXIR Hub and will thus be disseminated following ELIXIR Hub practices.